

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

UDC: 504.054

URBOECOLOGICAL MONITORING OF SOILS ALONG THE HIGHWAYS OF NASIMI DISTRICT OF BAKU CITY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7390933>

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the study of the ecological state of the soil cover of the Nasimi district of the city of Baku, which is a large industrial center. To do this, along with the chemical indicators of the soil, the level of pollution was determined and the ecological situation along the main highways of the city was assessed, the humus content and the level of pollution with heavy metals were studied to assess the soil. When assessing the soil cover along the major highways, it was found that the amount of humus in the soil is low, and it was found that the main pollutant is lead. In conclusion, the minimization of soil pollution along the main highways of Baku and modern measures to eliminate pollution of these soils were taken into account.

Keywords: highway networks, toxic gases, soil composition, metal pollution, degree of lead pollution.

Introduction: In a narrow sense, urbanization is the process of increasing the number of people living in a city. The increase in the urban population causes excessive pollution of the ecosystem. Currently, in 2022, more than 54% of the people living on earth live in cities, and the population explosion in cities continues. This number is expected to reach 66% in 2050. In 2008, the UN reported that 60% of the population will live in cities in the next twenty years. [1, p. four].

The territory we are exploring is the city of Baku. Baku is not only the industrial center of Azerbaijan, but also the center of science and culture. About 50% of the country's population lives in Baku. Many educational institutions of the country are located in this city. This city with an area of 2,430 km² has achieved great success in the construction of a highway network. Baku, the number one industrial center of Azerbaijan, is constantly developing and, as a result, systematically increasing the network of transport roads. One of the main provisions of the Master Plan "Development Concepts", "Azerbaijan 2020: A Look into the Future" is the development of an interdependent transport infrastructure throughout the country. One of the main issues facing the concept is the achievement of long-term socio-economic progress.

In accordance with this concept, new roads will be created and, as a result, time losses will be minimized. The territory of the route, along which corridors of international importance pass, will be expanded, roads will be built in accordance with world standards, city and settlement roads will be systematically reconstructed and asphalted. New bridges will be built and other old bridges will be repaired and upgraded. The flexibility of issues requiring a constructive solution will increase. The choice of the most suitable route option is a critical stage in the process of assessing the impact of the route on the environment. The highway should be built in such a way as to cause

minimal damage to the environment. The development of various modes of transport, especially cars, and the construction of roads has led to a multilateral increase in the direct and indirect impact of transport on a person. [2, p. 23-25]. The integrated implementation of these acts will reduce the impact of vehicles on the atmosphere. However, despite the implementation of large-scale acts, it cannot be said that the impact of vehicles on the environment has decreased. [3, p. 375-378].

Soils of the Absheron Peninsula: The transport-road complex remains a strong source of environmental pollution. 89% of 35 million tons of harmful waste is accounted for by road transport and road construction enterprises. The continuous increase in the number of cars has a certain negative impact on the environment and human health. [4, p. 10]. Areas relatively far from the habitat were selected for the construction of the road network. The peninsula is already surrounded by oil infrastructure from all directions. The high number of vehicles also creates high stress on urban land. When asphaltting the land, it causes the isolation of those areas, and as a result, the land cannot receive water and air. The inability to receive water and air brings the soil closer to a crisis in terms of nutrients. The toxic gases emitted by cars into the atmosphere are denser at a distance of 25-30 meters from the main highway. At that distance, toxic gases penetrate the soil without interruption. A car that moves at low speed and uses gasoline emits 0.05% of hydrocarbons into the atmosphere. Chemicals used in antifreeze cause more ecological imbalance on roads. Those substances lead to the drying of green trees, shrubs, and grasses. Considering that approximately 35% of transport is concentrated in other regions, we can see that Baku's transport load is too much. At this time, it is possible to estimate the amount of harmful substances released into the environment. The fact that the number of cars running on clean fuel is 5.01% complicates the

situation. The issue of reducing soil pollution to a minimum is reflected in the law of AR "Automobile Transport". In this law, which consists of 61 articles, the toxic gases of vehicles are divided into 6 classes according to the degree of danger. According to this law, all vehicles in the country must use Euro-4 standard fuel. Restrictions apply to mass passenger transport vehicles. [5, p. 229].

The use of vehicles, which leads to the disruption of the soil's water and micronutrient regime, and toxic gases emitted from highways make it difficult to protect the city's ecosystem. The strength indicator of urban

ecology is the soil of those areas. The base of the Absheron Peninsula is almost gray-brown soils. The humus content of the soil on the peninsula varies between 0.84-1.9%. Soils with low humus content and significantly lower absorption capacity prevail. Before the asphaltting work is carried out, according to the homogeneity of the top soil, the soil of the surface part is well filled or its stability is increased with concrete. The substances contained in the soil regulate the optical and electrochemical parameters of gray-brown soils. (Table 1.) [6, p. 72].

Table 1.

Properties of soils of the Absheron Peninsula

Type of soil cover structures	Depth along horizons, sm	Humus composition, %	CaCO ₃ , %	Evaluation carried out, %		Absorption amount, µg-eq
				<0,001 mm	<0,01 mm	
Gray-brown undeveloped soils of the radial-rounded type of the SPP of the foothill part	Ays 0-15	0,441	10,91	26,13	67,37	25,10
	AYB 15-30	0,449	17,21	36,13	69,01	23,01
Gray-brown swampy soils of the tree-like type of the SPP of the plain part	Ayvs, 0-15	1,91	21,10	8,25	23,13	20,81
	Ays 15-40	0,98	21,50	7,65	21,29	22,30

Currently, protecting land is one of the most important issues. For the sake of a healthier ecology, there is a need to study and apply international experience.

Research methods: The purpose of the research is to study the environmental changes occurring in the soil along the main highways of Nasimi region. More than 223,000 people live in the Nasimi district of Baku city, which has an area of 10 km² (Figure 1.)

Figure 1. Map of highways of Nasimi District of Baku city.

To determine the heavy metals in the soil, samples were taken as close as possible to highways. Samples were obtained at a temperature of 30-290°C. The surface layer of the soil was studied (0-15 cm). It was found that the closer the land is to the highway, the

more polluted it is. The most accumulation of metals occurs in the distance up to 22-26 m, which we consider as zone 1. Metals accumulate less in zone 2 due to air dispersion. That zone is up to 26-95 m. Heavy metals are not found in zone 3, which is 190 m away.

Table 2.

Metal content of the soil of Nasimi region, mg/kg

	Metals				
	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Pb
I	22,1	62,6	60,1	125,1	26,01
II	16	42,4	46,3	114,1	24,1
III	10,1	40,2	43,5	101	23,3

It is possible to make the heavy metals contained in the soil harmless and minimize their toxic effect by different methods. This purification occurs as a result of the reaction of compounds of lime (CaO) and phosphorus with different ionic charges with organic substances. [7, p. 172-175].

After 30,000-40,000 car drives, dangerous amounts of lead and carbon compounds are formed. 20% of lead falls in the form of exhaust gases in the form of aerosols, and 80% falls on the surface of the soil near the road in the form of solid particles up to 25 microns and dissolved in water. The maximum permissible level of lead in the soil according to the general sanitary indicator is 32 mg/kg, taking into account the background pollution. [8, p. 1-5].

Lead has a negative effect on our minds, it is especially dangerous for children. Children are more sensitive to the effects of toxic metal. The assessment of soil pollution around highways with lead waste from vehicles should be carried out on the basis of the considered pollution level of the surface layer of the soil. The level of lead contamination of the upper part of the soil from the edge of the roadway at different distances is determined by the formula:

$$P_s = \frac{P_p}{H * P} \quad (1)$$

Here;

P_s- lead pollution level of the surface layer of the soil (mg/kg);

H- the thickness of the soil layer where lead emissions are distributed;

P- density of soil (kg/m³).

The share of lead mg/m² on the earth's surface is determined by the formula.

$$P_p = 0,4 * K_1 * U_v * T_p * P_e + F \quad (2)$$

Here;

K₁- coefficient of consideration of the distance from the edge of the roadway;

U_v- the coefficient of variation depending on the strength and direction of the wind, taken from the edge of the road opposite the intended zone, is equal to the ratio of the area of the wind rise to its total area;

T_p - the estimated life of the road in days, 7300 days correspond to a twenty-year prospective period;

F- background pollution of the earth's surface;

P_e- is the average daily lead emission power.

In general, taking into account the toxic components contained in gases, complex measures should be taken to reduce them to permissible levels in the country.(Table 3.)

Table 3.

The maximum permissible concentration of toxic compounds in the exhaust gases in the atmosphere of Baku, mg/m³

Lead compounds	Degree of danger	Maximum permissible concentration during the day, mg/m ³
Carbon monoxide (CO)	4	3,01
Hydrocarbons (C _x H _x)	3	1,50
Nitrogen oxides (NO _x)	2	0,041
Lead (Pb) and its compounds	1	0,0013

➤ The choice of protective measures should be made on the basis of technical and economic comparison of the following important ways:

➤ Changing road parameters (value) based on the average speed of motor vehicles;

➤ Changing or restricting the movement of different vehicles at different intervals:

➤ Increasing control over the movement of motor vehicles with irregular engines in the area sensitive to air pollution in order to minimize toxic waste emitted into the air;

➤ Design of protective constructions. [9, p. 120-142].

Lead is mainly adsorbed by the surface of clay particles, organic compounds, manganese oxides, iron and aluminum hydroxides. If we pay attention to metals, lead is less mobile among them, which is explained by the limited amount of lead in the soil solution. Accumulation of lead in the upper humus horizon is observed for all soils, including natural landscapes.

Roads are polluted with toxic compounds all the time and experts are coming up with solutions to eliminate them. According to scientists, the most convenient way is to increase the branches of the roads. Another issue is improving the quality of sewage water.

But all these issues require high investment. On roads with light soils, toxic substances are more easily mixed with the soil, and it is practically impossible to neutralize them. In order to reduce the penetration of toxic substances into the layers of the soil, it is necessary to increase the buffer properties of the soil. For this, it is necessary to feed the soil, that is, to give it fertilizers. [10, p. 2771-2773].

Vehicles that pollute the air should be reduced to a minimum and environmentally friendly transport should be used. In the middle of the 21st century, the creation of a tram line in Baku is considered. There are more than 1,300,000 vehicles in Azerbaijan. Throughout the year, an amount of pollution is released into the atmosphere of Baku city from the exhaust gases of vehicles, equal to its own weight. If we take the weight of a car as approximately 400 kg, 400,000 tons of pollutants enter the atmosphere of Baku every year. Cars should be produced as light as possible and the less fuel used should significantly reduce the damage to the ecosystem. Comprehensive forecasting along with years-ahead solutions will improve the environmental situation and, as a result, future generations will not remember urban pollution as a heavy legacy of the past.

Results:

1)The humus content of the soil and the location dependence of heavy metals along the transport infrastructure of Baku were determined. In the samples taken from the approved zones of Nasimi district of Baku city, it was determined that the adsorption capacity of the soil is much lower, and as a result, the stability of the soil is weak.

2)The Concept was adopted and foreign experience was studied for the implementation of complex measures to improve the ecology of the country. The analysis of the results of the researches made it possible to determine the degree of importance and necessity of the rapid implementation of measures to improve the ecology of the soil in Baku.

3)Among the heavy metals, the most dangerous pollutant is lead compounds and it is necessary to localize them in the soil without migrating.

The obtained results can be used in organizing the ecological atlas, land maps and schemes of Baku city.

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